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D4.4 Investigation of new methods for establishing state of health of the batteries and the development of methods for testing battery conditions to verify state of health

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
AC	Alternating current
ACIR	Alternating current internal resistance
BESS	Battery energy storage system
BIU	Battery interface unit
BMS	Battery management system
CCCV	Constant current constant voltage
CV	Constant voltage
CC	Constant current
CEI	Cathode electrolyte interphase
D	Deliverable report
DC	Direct current
DCIR	Direct current internal resistance
ECO	ECO STOR AS
ECM	Equivalent circuit model
EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
EKOF	Ekokumpanit Oy (EcoFellows)
EV	Electric vehicle
GITT	Galvanostatic intermittent titration technique
ICI	Intermittent current interruption
IEA	International Energy Agency
KVC-DEMO	Key value chain demonstration
LIB	Li-ion battery
LFP	Li-iron-phosphate (LiFePO ₄)
NMC	Li-nickel-manganese-cobalt-oxide (LiNi _x Mn _y Co _z O ₂)
NCA	Li-nickel-cobalt-aluminium-oxide (LiNi _x Co _y Al _z O ₂)
OCV	Open circuit voltage
SEI	Solid electrolyte interphase
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
SoH	State of health
SoC	State of charge
XCT	X-ray computed tomography
XPS	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
XRF	X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy

Executive Summary

Information about a battery's state of health (SoH) is essential to enable safe operation of both smaller and larger batteries. Additionally, it is vital to diagnose SoH for batteries intended for repurposing or 2nd life use. A poorly diagnosed battery put into a new application can lead to thermal runaway and fatal accidents. With full access to the battery management system (BMS) and user history, SoH diagnostics would be much quicker and less costly. However, this is often not the case for most 2nd life stakeholders. Thus, they must go through time consuming and costly battery diagnostics routines in order to make sure that the used batteries are suitable for their new application. In this work, we have explored two different diagnostic techniques on battery modules, which are most commonly used on single cells. These are galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and intermittent current interruption (ICI). Both techniques can be performed by a 2nd life stakeholder without more advanced equipment than a programmable battery tester. The data does require some handling in order to extract all the useful information. However, this is not extremely complex and can be done by relatively simple programming. Data obtained from these two methods include charge and discharge curves, which gives remaining capacity and polarization. Both GITT and ICI are based on charging and discharging while introducing either short (a few seconds) and frequent current interruptions or longer (in minutes) and less frequent interruptions/relaxations. Open circuit voltage (OCV) are measured during the current interruptions/relaxations and can then be used to calculate both instantaneous and total resistance of the battery. While ICI provides a larger amount of resistance values across the state of charge (SoC) window compared to GITT, GITT will also give equilibrium OCV for the different SoC where relaxation is performed.

In this report, we have been able to measure GITT and ICI on battery modules from two different electric vehicles (EVs). Six of the battery modules were from a relatively new EV with estimated SoH at 96%, while the other six modules were estimated to have 84% SoH. This provided us with battery modules with very different user history and degradation. The obtained data shows that GITT and ICI both can be very useful techniques for diagnosing a battery's SoH. However, for GITT and ICI to provide accurate information and be useful on degraded batteries, it is quite essential to have data for new batteries to compare. Otherwise, it will not be possible to see how much resistance, capacity and polarization has changed over time.

In addition to the experimental work, an introduction to different Li-ion battery (LiB) chemistries and their degradation mechanisms are provided. This is meant to give the reader an understanding of the complexity of LiBs and why proper SoH diagnostics can be very difficult and time-consuming.

1. INTRODUCTION

Existing and upcoming challenges for extending electric vehicle battery lifetime were elaborated in a previous report delivered for the TREASoURcE project (D4.1). Here, 10 main challenges were identified within the four areas technical challenges, regulations & legislations, eco-design, and safety & reliability. All four areas are to some extent connected, as for example safety and reliability are affected by some of the technical challenges, and technical challenges are again related to both eco-design and regulations and legislation. As an example, current legislation does not ensure access to all necessary historical data for safe reuse of EV batteries, and this affects how batteries can be reused in a safe manner in addition to necessitating costly test procedures. The EU Battery Regulation is now effective and will in time mitigate some of the current challenges. Particularly the implementation of a Battery Passport containing important information, will ensure access to more information than what is currently available to 2nd life stakeholders. However, it will take quite a long time before significant amounts of used EV batteries with Battery Passports are ready for the 2nd life market. Thus, in the meantime it is important to find new and more effective ways of assessing battery state of health (SoH) for safe reuse of EV batteries in stationary storage or other less demanding applications. In this report we will focus more specifically on the technical challenges related to assessing SoH of battery modules. Additionally, there will be a section elaborating on the current test procedures used at ECO STOR for assessment of battery packs and their suitability for 2nd life applications.

In order to understand the complexity of Li-ion batteries (LIBs) and their degradation mechanisms, a brief introduction to LIBs is provided. This includes explanations on the main parts of a LIB cell, how it's built and the different LIB chemistries. As an introduction to the experimental testing, different approaches for SoH estimation are described in chapter 2. Here, the different methods are compared in terms of accuracy, type of data collected and whether they are useful tools in larger scale operations. The two main analysis methods used for the modules in this report are also given a brief introduction to give the reader a better understanding of their advantages and limitations and which type of information can be expected. The two methods explored here, are galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and intermittent current interruption (ICI), both of which provide information on internal resistance of the batteries and data that can be used to extract information on diffusion resistance coefficients. GITT also provides information on open circuit voltage (OCV) for different states of charge (SoC).

In the experimental section, a more detailed explanation of the experiments is provided and how the battery modules and battery packs are assessed. Results and discussion in chapter 4 provides the most essential data, while data for all the modules are compiled in ANNEX 1 and 2.

2. Background

In order to accurately assess a battery's state of health (SoH), it is important to have as much information as possible about the battery's chemistry and user history. The latter is often not possible to access and thus a variety of different test methods have been developed over the years for assessing SoH. Some of the methods are destructive and not suitable for batteries intended for further use. Other methods are non-destructive, but often suffer from reduced accuracy and do not provide all necessary information. Zhu et al. have established a general overview of a procedure used for repurposing of EV batteries, which includes 5 main steps (Zhu J, 2021):

1. Incoming assessment
2. Disassembly
3. Mechanical, electrochemical and safety performance evaluation
4. Sorting and regrouping
5. Developing control strategies for second life applications

This report will not go in detail about each step, as this is described in more detail in TREASoURcE deliverable D4.1. (Galteland, Gouis, Vullum-Bruer, McDougall, & Thorsen, 2023) However, in the following sections step 3 above will be given a more thorough review.

2.1. Li-ion battery chemistries

Li-ion batteries (LIBs) are often categorized by their cathode material. The most common EV cathode chemistries are NMC (lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide), LFP (lithium iron phosphate), and NCA (lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide). There are variations of the NMC cathode chemistries with various fractions of the elements, like NMC111 (1/3 Ni, 1/3 Mn, 1/3 Co), NMC523, NMC622, NMC721, and NMC811, in order of increasing nickel content. NMC111 is the only material deviating from the regular nomenclature, where "1" refers to 1/3. The historical development in the global cathode market shares is shown in Figure 1. (Takahashi, 2025) It is evident that NMC blends have dominated the LIB market, while LFP has experienced a renewed interest in the last few years. According to predictions by the International Energy Agency (IEA) LFP sales shares are expected to continue growing (IEA, 2022). NMC has inherently higher specific energy density but suffers from shorter lifetime and lower thermal stability. In addition, fluctuating market prices for nickel and cobalt and a desire to reduce or remove the use of cobalt, has caused LFP to gain market shares as EV batteries. The next generation batteries, such as various

Figure 1: Historical development in the global Li-ion battery chemistry market share. Figure from (Takahashi, 2025).

lithium-ion all-solid-state batteries, are expected to reach the market in the near future. For example, Chinese automaker Changan Automobile has revealed plans to begin mass production of solid-state batteries by 2027, if vehicle testing succeeds in 2026. Changan hopes to test its all-solid-state batteries in prototype vehicles already by the end of 2025. (Daly, 2025)

The cell voltage of the nickel-based cathodes is between 3.6-4.5 V, while the cell voltage of LFP is between 3.0-3.3V. As a result, the nickel-based cathodes have a higher energy and power density than LFP cells. (J. Jyoti, 2021) LFP has a longer cycle lifetime and is about 30% less expensive than nickel-based cathodes. (Lombardo, Paoli, Pales, & Gül, 2025) The expected cycling lifetime of LFP is between 2000-3000 cycles, while for nickel-based cathodes the expected cycling lifetime is between 1000 to 2000 cycles. (Battery University, n.d.) The LFP cathodes are considered more stable than nickel-based cathodes, as LFP cells hit thermal runaway around 195 °C, while the NMC cells hit thermal runaway around 170 °C, depending on the specific chemistries and conditions (Duh, et al., 2021). In addition, the materials in LFP cells are less toxic than substances such as cobalt and nickel in NMC cells (Sun, Bisschop, Niu, & Huang, 2020). NMC cathodes contain higher concentrations of valuable metals (nickel, cobalt, manganese), making them more profitable to recycle than LFP cathodes where the amount of valuable materials is low (Baum, Bird, Yu, & Ma, 2022).

2.2. Battery degradation parameters

In order to understand the complexity of SoH assessments, it is important to give a brief overview of the inside of a Li-ion battery (LIB) cell and how different chemistries affect the properties and degradation mechanisms. A LIB consists of a few main components as illustrated in Figure 2, where the graphite anode and lithium metal oxide cathode are the active electrode materials. The electrolyte is typically lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) dissolved in an organic solvent containing linear and

Figure 2: Illustration of a Li-ion battery showing graphite on copper current collector on the left, electrolyte with separator in the middle and lithium metal oxide cathode on aluminium current collector on the right. (Illustration: SINTEF)

cyclic carbonates. The separator separates the anode and cathode and is typically either a polyethylene or polypropylene porous film. The liquid electrolyte ensures transport of Li-ions between the anode and cathode, while the current collectors on each side facilitate transport of electrons through the outer circuit. During charging, the Li-ions (pink spheres) are transported from the cathode to the anode through the electrolyte, while electrons move from the cathode to the anode through an external circuit. This happens due to an externally applied voltage (i.e. plugging in your device for charging), which drives the transport of electrons and ions. Upon discharge, the opposite occurs, where Li-ions move from the anode to the cathode accompanied by electrons in an outer circuit which can be used to power a device. This process is reversible and can be repeated hundreds and thousands of times. However, in addition to the wanted reactions inside the battery, there are always additional reactions occurring, which contribute to the degradation and ageing of the battery. A thorough review of LIB degradation is provided by Rahman and Alharbi (Rahman & Alharbi, 2024), and an illustration is provided below from Birkel et al. (Birkel, Roberts, McTurk, Bruce, & Howey, 2017). Below follows a very short summary of the main degradation mechanisms and their consequences.

Figure 3: Degradation mechanisms inside a Li-ion battery. Figure from (Birkel, Roberts, McTurk, Bruce, & Howey, 2017)

2.2.1. Anode and electrolyte degradation mechanisms

As Figure 3 illustrates, there are many different mechanisms leading to the degradation and capacity loss of a LIB. Degradation of anode and electrolyte are quite closely connected and often interdependent. On the anode the most prominent reactions involve the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) and lithium metal dendrite formation. The SEI contains decomposition products from the electrolyte and forms due to instability of the electrolyte at the given electrode operating voltages. SEI formation causes loss of lithium inventory as well as leading to increased internal resistance of the cell through hindering or slowing down transport of electrons and ions. Increased internal resistance will again lead to increased heat evolution during charging/discharging, which further accelerates electrolyte decomposition and can in worst case lead to thermal runaway. At the same time, SEI is vital for

the operation and lifetime of the battery as it prevents further direct contact between the electrolyte and the electrode and thereby slowing down further SEI growth.

Lithium metal plating and dendrite formation can cause internal short circuits, which may also end in thermal runaway. The process of lithium plating is accelerated at low temperatures and during fast charging of the battery. This shows how important user history of an EV, particularly in which climate it is used, can be for SoH assessments as f.ex. EVs driven in the Nordics will be much more exposed to cold temperatures compared to southern Europe. On the other hand, higher temperatures may lead to accelerated degradation of the electrolyte, which is more likely to occur in countries with warmer climates.

Other anode degradation mechanisms include particle cracking due to mechanical stress, solvent co-intercalation and graphite exfoliation in addition to delamination from the current collector. The latter can be caused by copper dissolution and cracking. Delamination will lead to increased internal resistance and eventually loss of contact and cell death. Particle cracking also accelerates SEI growth as new surface is exposed to the electrolyte and initiates additional electrolyte decomposition.

2.2.2. Cathode degradation mechanisms

Degradation mechanisms on the cathode side are mainly governed by the changes in the active cathode material leading to loss of Li-ion storage capacity, reduced Li-ion transport and particle cracking and disintegration. There is also a cathode electrolyte interphase (CEI) similar to the SEI on the anode. However, this is much less pronounced and does not cause equally severe degradation issues. One of the main challenges on the cathode side is dissolution of transition metals (i.e. Mn, Ni, Co) into the electrolyte. This occurs particularly for Mn, which tends to dissolve into the electrolyte and migrate through the electrolyte and deposit on the anode surface. The dissolved transition metal can also chemically decompose the bulk electrolyte. (Hestenes, Sadowski, May, & Marbella, 2023) In addition to contaminating the anode, transition metal dissolution also causes deterioration of the cathode through severe structural changes, leading to loss of active material. Structural changes in the cathode may also occur even in the absence of transition metal dissolution. In NMC-based materials cation mixing is one of the main degradation mechanisms. Here, nickel ions migrate into lithium sites and block lithium migration within the cathode. Other cathode degradation mechanisms include particle cracking and aluminium corrosion. The latter leads to delamination of the active material from the current collector, which increases internal resistance and eventually cause cell death. Particle cracking is caused by mechanical tension in the cathode powder particles and is a result of the volume changes experienced during charging and discharging of the battery.

2.3. Strategies for evaluating battery degradation

Evaluation of a used battery can be done on pack-, module- or cell-level. The most accurate and detailed results will come from cell-level evaluations. However, this requires the battery pack to be completely disassembled, which may not be the most economic solution due to the relatively large

manual efforts involved in the disassembly. Evaluation at module-level can still give some valuable results. Although some methods may not be relevant or feasible on module-level. With access to the battery pack BMS, it would also be possible to do a more detailed evaluation on pack-level. However, this is often not possible. Thus, pack-level evaluation will require a whole different set of methods, evaluation criteria and modelling tools to provide useful information.

According to Zhu et al. (Zhu J, 2021), there are three strategies for evaluating battery degradation:

1. Post-mortem examination-based
2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and equivalent circuit model (ECM) based
3. Charge-discharge curve-based

2.3.1. Post-mortem examination

Post-mortem examination is performed at cell-level. This method is typically destructive and includes opening the battery cell. Post-mortem analysis therefore gives by far the most detailed and accurate evaluation of the battery's SoH. Combining different advanced materials characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction, different types of spectroscopy (i.e. XRF, XPS, Raman), and scanning and/or transmission electron spectroscopy, post-mortem analysis provides very accurate information about how the battery has degraded. Although this is obviously not a technique suitable for batteries that are meant to be reused, it is possible to correlated post-mortem analysis with different types of non-destructive methods such that it is feasible to get quite good estimates for SoH without destroying the battery. Non-destructive X-ray computed tomography (XCT) can also be performed at cell-level. This method could potentially provide valuable information. However, it is not a very established method and currently just used for research purposes.

2.3.2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and equivalent circuit model (ECM)

EIS can be performed at both cell and module level, although it is most commonly used at cell level. EIS is a method where a small AC voltage (typically a few millivolts) is applied to an electrochemical system over a range of frequencies, and the resulting current response is measured. This response is used to calculate the impedance of the system, giving an imaginary and a real part. The data is normally represented in a Nyquist plot. Figure 4 shows a schematic of an electrochemical cell with accompanying Nyquist plot and equivalent circuit. Through fitting the equivalent circuit model to the obtained data, EIS can give insight into various physical and chemical processes occurring in the system. (Lazanas & Prodromidis, 2023) Interpreting EIS data can be quite a complex task, as many of the signals from a full battery cell may overlap. De-convoluting the data into meaningful information is thus not straight forward. EIS-based techniques are therefore currently only used for research or in the laboratory and are not yet suited for commercial use (Zhu J, 2021). Thus, the development of non-destructive assessment methods is important for repurposing.

Figure 4: Schematic of an electrochemical test cell, with example of a Nyquist plot (top right) and the equivalent circuit representing this cell. Figure adapted from (Lazanas & Prodromidis, 2023). Text box explains the different acronyms.

2.3.3. Charge-discharge curves and potential relaxation

In the work presented in the further chapter of this report, we have chosen to focus on using charge-discharge profiles and potential relaxations to be able to calculate internal resistance of the cell. There are particularly two different methods which we have chosen to focus on. One is galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT), and the other is intermittent current interruption (ICI), both of which are based on calculating resistance from relaxation curves or potential drops. Relaxing a battery means that the applied potential is removed for a shorter or longer period of time, and then the open circuit voltage is measured during this time period. Both GITT and ICI have been used extensively for single cell analysis. However, neither are commonly used on modules, and it is not previously done to the systematic extent shown in this report.

Intermittent current interruption (ICI)

In addition to capacity, resistance of the battery is one of the main parameters used to estimate a battery's SoH. Measuring capacity is relatively straight forward and is usually done by a constant current/constant voltage (CCCV) or constant current (CC) discharge test. Measuring resistance of a battery is less straight forward as it originates from several complex processes within the battery. We often refer to both direct current internal resistance (DCIR) and alternating current internal resistance (ACIR), which are measured using different methods. While DCIR is the least complex method, it only provides information on the ohmic resistance, which does not distinguish between different processes in the cell. EIS, mentioned in the previous section, can provide more detailed information, but requires much more specialized equipment. An alternative to DCIR and EIS, is ICI, which was developed by Lacey and co-workers for quicker and improved battery diagnostics. (Lacey, Edström, & Brandell, 2015) (Lacey, 2017) (Chien, Menon, Brant, Brandell, & Lacey, 2020) (Aktekin, et al., 2018) (Hernández, et al., 2020) (Yin, et al., 2022) By using ICI, it is in principle possible to determine both ohmic resistance and diffusion resistance coefficient, which can be correlated to the diffusion coefficient extracted from EIS measurements. (Yin, et al., 2022)

ICI is performed by cycling (full charge and discharge cycle) a battery cell or module at CCCV at moderate to low current density to be able to treat the charge transfer resistance as ohmic. A current interruption of only a few seconds is introduced at a set interval. The interval is chosen so that the

cycling protocol would allow for approximately 60 current interruptions per charge or discharge. This will enable resistance calculations along the whole SoC window from 0 to 100%. A typical potential change with time for a single cell measurement is shown in Figure 5. Here it can be seen that the voltage first goes through an instantaneous change (arrow a), followed by a considerably slower one (arrow b). The influence of time-dependent sub-processes can then be calculated from the voltage response, which is recorded frequently during the current interruption. The approach used by Yin

Figure 5: Typical potential change with time during current interruption. Arrow a shows the instantaneous change after the current is switched off, while arrow b corresponds to the following more slowly changed potential. (Yin, et al., 2022)

et al on a single cell is transferred to measurements done for a battery module in this work. The potential change with time response will look very similar for a battery module, only measured at much higher voltages compared to a single cell.

Galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT)

GITT is somewhat similar to the ICI method in that they both measure voltage relaxation. However, in GITT the relaxation time is in the order of minutes rather than seconds. The GITT measures the transient voltage change and open-circuit voltage (OCV) change during the charging and discharging processes using only a constant current supply and specified cut-off intervals. (Kim, Park, Hwang, & Yoon, 2022) The method was developed already in the 1970s and can provide both thermodynamic and kinetic parameters from an electrochemical cell. The GITT can calculate diffusivity values, and thereby resistance values, at various SoC simply by monitoring the voltage change during OCV. Additionally, OCV at different SoC is another useful parameter that is obtained from GITT measurements.

GITT is based on the idea that the number of ions passing through the electrolyte can be calculated from the current. (Kim, Park, Hwang, & Yoon, 2022) By using Fick's law, equations can be derived for calculating the number of mobile ions moving at the interface between the electrolyte and the electrode phase boundary, correlating with the transient and steady-state voltage measurements. Figure 6 is a schematic illustrating a single GITT measurement with the current and voltage signals in (b) and (c) and the corresponding ongoing processes in (d). The cell starts in an equilibrium state, where the concentration of mobile ions is homogeneous throughout the electrode. When a constant current pulse (I_0) is applied at time t_0 , a sudden voltage step occurs from E_1 to E_2 owing to the current flux in the form of an IR drop (the voltage increases or decreases when the current is positive or negative, respectively). Electrode processes are often kinetically controlled, and the voltage drop is normally more pronounced for higher current values. In this report, we will be utilizing the IR drop during both charge and discharge of the battery modules. For the

interested reader, a more detailed description of the derived equations and calculations used in the GITT method, can be found in a review paper by Kim et al. (Kim, Park, Hwang, & Yoon, 2022)

Figure 6: Schematic illustration of an electrochemical cell with an insertion electrode (B) and a metal counter electrode (A), showing also current (b) and voltage (c) signals during a GITT step, accompanied by the processes ongoing in the host material (d). (Kim, Park, Hwang, & Yoon, 2022)

3. Experimental procedures and data handling

The following chapter will describe the battery modules tested and methods used for the battery module analysis. A section on battery pack testing performed by ECO STOR is also included. The first section describes the battery modules, and the information provided about the modules. The second section describes the electrochemical testing of the batteries, while the third section describes how the data was handled, including calculations performed for estimating internal resistance of the new and used battery modules. The fourth and final section describes the battery pack testing performed by ECO STOR.

3.1. Description of battery modules and their properties

The battery modules are from two different electric vehicles (EVs). The information provided was very limited, thus some information has been obtained from the Electric Vehicle Database (Electric Vehicle Database, 2025). In the table below are the main information received in addition to calculated values for a single module. The calculations are based on 12 modules per battery pack.

Table 1: Battery pack and module specifications.

Property	Unit	Data for full battery pack	Data for one module (calculated)
V_{rated}	V	360	30
V_{min}	V	240	20
V_{max}	V	400	33.3
$P_{max_discharge}$ (10 sec, 25 °C)	kW	70	5.83
P_{max_charge} (10 sec, 25 °C)	kW	40	3.33
Nominal energy new pack	kWh	25.92	2.16
Net energy new pack	kWh	22	1.83
Nominal capacity new pack	Ah	72	72
Net capacity new pack	Ah	61.1	61.1

We also know that the battery chemistry is NMC, but we do not know the ratio of Ni, Mn and Co. However, NMC batteries typically operate within a voltage range of 3.0 to 4.2 V per cell. From the Electric Vehicle Database we have found that each battery pack contains 192 battery cells, which gives 16 cells per module. With the information provided, we can then calculate how many batteries are placed in series and parallel within each module.

For batteries connected in series: $V_{total} = V_1 + V_2 + V_3 + \dots + V_n$

For batteries connected in parallel: $V_{total} = V_1 = V_2 = V_3 = \dots = V_n$

Here n is the total number of batteries connected in series or parallel. Thus, for the modules provided here we find that there must be two parallel series of 8 batteries in each for one module.

SINTEF received a total of 12 modules from ECO STOR, which they have obtained from their EV partner. 6 of these modules were from a relatively new battery pack, where the estimated state of health (SoH) was 96%. The other 6 modules were from a battery pack which had been in use for quite some time and was estimated to have SoH at 84%. Figure 7 shows how the modules were placed with respect to each other in the battery pack.

Figure 7: This illustration shows how the modules are placed with respect to each other in the battery pack. There are also modules next to 5 and 6, but these we did not have access to test.

3.2. Electrochemical testing of battery modules

All the electrochemical tests were performed using a CE-6016n-60V30A-H battery cycler from Neware shown in Figure 8. Two channels were coupled in parallel for the GITT tests requiring currents above 30 A. All tests were performed at room temperature around 23 to 24 °C.

Due to the lack of information about the battery modules, a series of charge and discharge cycles were performed in order to get familiar with the battery modules. Charge and discharge were performed at relatively high currents, up to 60 A, while the modules were constantly monitored. We did not have the possibility to measure temperature inside the module, so only temperature on the surface of the module could be monitored. During the initial charging and discharging it was found that noticeable heating occurred in the 84% SoH modules at 60 A current. While the 96% SoH module did not experience significant heating after a full charge at 60 A. For further testing, it was thus determined to keep the maximum current at 45 A for the 84% SoH modules, while the less aged modules could be tested at 60 A.

Figure 8: Photo of the Neware battery cycler together with one of the battery modules being tested.

Two different test regimes were performed for all 12 modules. These were galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and intermittent current interruption (ICI). Both techniques have been described previously in this report, and data from both methods can be used to calculate the resistance of the modules. Before the full cycle was started, the modules were first discharged by constant current/constant voltage (CCCV) to 20 V with a 6 A cutoff current. This ensures that the modules are fully discharged before the charging starts. The modules (both 84% SoH and 96% SoH) were then charged to 33.3 V using a constant current (CC) of 12 A, which correlates to a C-rate between 0.15C and 0.2C (1C is the current required to fully charge or fully discharge a battery within 1 hour). The charge was immediately followed by a full discharge at the same current down to 20 V. A relatively low current was chosen to be able to assume that the charge transfer resistance is ohmic. A 3 sec current interruption was introduced every 5 min (for 84% SoH) or every 6 min (for 96% SoH) until the battery was fully charged. The difference in timing between the current interruptions was introduced to ensure at least 60 measuring points per charge or discharge.

GITT measurements were performed at 60 A for the 96% SoH modules and 45 A for the 84% SoH modules. Also here, the modules were first discharged at CCCV down to 20 V with a 6 A cutoff current to ensure that the modules were fully discharged. The GITT was performed by constant current charging at 45 A or 60 A with 5 min relaxations. Relaxations were performed at the following state of charge (SoC): 2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, 10%, 30%, 50%, 70%, 90%, 92%, 94%, 96%, 98%, and 100%. The same was performed on discharge. It is expected that the internal resistances will experience greater change at low and high SoC, thus the frequency of the relaxations are higher in these intervals. The relaxations are performed by simply cutting the current and leaving the battery module to relax while measuring the voltage during this time period.

3.3. Data handling and calculation of internal resistance

The experimental ICI and GITT data were plotted and analysed to better understand the batteries and to obtain resistances for the batteries. The key resistance findings for all batteries and modules are given in Figure 11, while details for module 2 (BAT 1 and BAT 2) are given in Figure 12. The rest of the detailed module plots can be found in Annex 1 and 2.

For both ICI and GITT (described in section 2.3.3), a key part of analysing the data was to find the interruptions (Figure 5) and pulses (Figure 6b). This was done by finding all time indices where a change in current larger than 1 ampere occurred. This gives the start and end indices for the interruptions and the pulses, labelled t_{start} and t_{end} . For ICI t_{start} was defined to be the last datapoint before the interruption, and t_{end} the last datapoint before the current was restored. For GITT it was defined in the same way, just with current pulses instead of interruptions. I.e., t_{start} was the last datapoint before pulse was finished, and t_{end} the last datapoint before the next current pulse was applied. Next, the associated voltage drops were calculated. V_{inst} is the instantaneous voltage drop, calculated as the difference in potential between t_{start} and $t_{start+1}$. V_{tot} is the total voltage drop, which corresponds to the difference in voltage between t_{start} and t_{end} . The resistances were then simply calculated as:

$$R_{tot} = \frac{V_{tot}}{\Delta I}$$

$$R_{inst} = \frac{V_{inst}}{\Delta I}$$

ΔI simplifies to the current of the pulse in the case of GITT, and to the current by which the slow charging is performed in the case of ICI.

3.4. State of health tests on full battery packs

A full overview of the SoH of a battery pack would require tests on module and cell level, such as those described in the previous sections on modules. These tests involve opening the battery pack which involves both risk, cost and is time consuming. If the battery pack is reused without dismantling it, it is possible save work hours and it is possible to take advantage of the safety measures and functionality provided by the original manufacturer to a greater extent.

This approach leads to a need of a way to evaluate the SoH and suitability for second life use for the whole battery pack. If a battery pack is to be used as a whole, it is important to determine that no component is in bad shape, as one faulty component may be enough to make the whole pack unusable. For example, if there is 1 faulty cell in the battery pack, this non-functioning cell can disrupt the neighbouring cells, making them faulty, or in worst case start a thermal runaway. Consequently, one faulty cell typically means that the battery pack cannot be used and should instead be recycled or dismantled.

If the battery pack has no obvious faulty components, it is still important to evaluate the remaining capacity for several reasons. First, to decide whether the remaining capacity of the battery pack is so low that the work to produce a secondary battery system exceeds the benefit of second life use. Secondly, for classifying and managing the battery packs effectively, the capacity needs to be known. For longevity, it's important that that battery packs grouped together is as similar as possible and the load management considers the real SoH of each battery pack in the battery energy storage system (BESS).

To estimate the SoH and suitability for second life use on a battery pack level, a battery pack test was developed. Based on theory and experience with faulty battery packs, 6 issues were chosen to assess whether a battery pack is not suitable for second life use:

1. There is visible physical damage on the battery pack
2. The manufacturer's BMS is not working.
3. The manufacturer's BMS is reporting errors.
4. There are battery cells in the battery pack which are faulty
5. The internal resistance of the battery is too high.
6. The capacity of the battery is too low

To test this, a battery pack test was developed. On a battery pack level, it was required to communicate with battery manufacturer's BMS, which typically measures and reports cell voltages, temperatures, current, isolation resistance and errors. ECO STOR has designed a battery interface unit (BIU) that can be used to communicate with the manufacturer's BMS. Most BMSs communicate through CAN-communication, and so the BIU is designed to be able to extract these values from the BMS and forward them. While each manufacturer's BMS and battery pack are different, some information is standardized. ECO STOR's BIU identify these common parameters, and use these in the battery test, so that the same battery test can be performed on battery packs from different manufacturers.

To communicate with the manufacturer's BMS however, it is usually necessary to have the BMS's CAN database and other information, such as the OCV-curve, which is typically restricted information. Consequently, cooperation with the manufacturer is currently required. However, in the future it may be possible to access this information without the help of the manufacturer. The EU Battery Regulation requires all new batteries (larger than 2 kWh) placed on the market from 2027 onwards to have a battery passport, which may also include access rights to the information described above. (European Parliament, 2023)

The battery pack test was divided into 3 parts: Visual inspection, digital inspection and power cycle. The tests were performed chronologically in this order, designed to start with the quickest and easiest tests first, so that the non-suitable batteries could be filtered out as quickly as possible.

Visual inspection

A visual inspection was an effective way to quickly get an impression of the state of the battery. Any physical damage, such as any deformation on the battery pack, missing parts, strong odour or extensive amount of rust, would rule out the battery for use in second life application. The exterior condition of the battery pack may differ from the battery cells and modules inside the battery pack. However, a poor conditioned exterior, highly increases the probability that there has been significant mechanical stress or that the battery has been used in harsh conditions or been stored inappropriately.

Digital inspection

If the visual inspection is approved, a digital inspection of the manufacturer's BMS is performed. The advantage of the digital inspection is that it requires little work to set up and many parameters can quickly be assessed. Additionally, we get access to potential issues reported by the BMS itself, that may be difficult or impossible to find in another test. A movable test rig was created (Figure 9), with the BIU and a test script stored on a tablet, allowing quick connection and automatic testing. During the test, the manufacturer's BMS is turned on and values are extracted and analysed.

Figure 9: A movable digital inspection rig was created, allowing quick inspection of stored batteries. The BIU (grey box on the left side of the rig) is connected directly to the battery pack's BMS

The following tests were performed chronologically during the digital inspection:

- Turn on BMS. Evaluate if communication is established and that the BMS is turned on within the expected time limit. A slow BMS may indicate that the BMS is faulty.
- Check if the communication between the BIU and BMS is without errors. Slow communication, missing CAN-frames or responses, indicates either a problem with the BMS, or possibly the BIU, test equipment or test setup.
- Check if the BMS is reporting any battery errors. The manufacturer's BMS is typically designed to look for errors such as insulation and battery cell issues.
- Check SoH reported by the BMS. If the reported SoH was too low, a battery would be considered not worth using in a second life application. A high value reported for SoH by the BMS, is not a guarantee for an actual high SoH, but a very low reported SoH is not worth ignoring.

- Check cell voltage ranges. A high difference between the highest and lowest voltage indicates that one or several cells may be faulty or unevenly aged.
- Close and open contactor. Check that the contactors open and close as expected, and that the BMS is not reporting new errors during this process.

Power cycle test

If all the tests in the digital inspection passes, the battery pack could move on to the power cycle test, which monitors the battery pack while being charged and discharged. To charge and discharge the battery, ITECH bi-directional Power supply IT6018C-1500-40, was used. With this device, it was possible to measure the current and battery voltage, independently of the BMS. This was also useful to be able to compare different types of battery packs and BMS, and the data could be used to more accurately decide what limits where “acceptable” for each type of BMS. The power cycle test also allowed monitoring of the BMS and battery under load, which could reveal battery errors that would not be active during the digital inspection.

An automated power cycle test was created, as illustrated in Figure 10, consisting of 4 steps: (1) Charge with 0.25 C for t minutes; (2) Stop power and wait t minutes; (3) Discharge 0.25 C for t minutes; (4) Stop power and wait t minutes.

Figure 10: The power cycle illustrated by current and voltage and measurement points

With the OCV-curve, it was possible to use the measured battery pack voltage to find the corresponding SoC. The reasoning for not using the BMS reported SoC, was to get an independent estimate, as testing had showed that the SoC and SoH reported by the BMS could be inaccurate and increasingly so with aged batteries. The waiting period before measurement, was to let the battery voltage stabilize after power was applied to it, ensuring that the battery is at equilibrium.

The capacity was then calculated by taking the measured energy usage and divide it on the SoC change. The internal resistance was found by a simple current interruption test, using Ohm’s Law over the voltage change from when current is applied to the battery, and then immediately after it is cut, during the power cycle. While this power cycle test offered a quick estimation of the capacity and

internal resistance of the whole battery pack in one test cycle, it should be mentioned that it is also simplified and flawed. A more accurate estimation of the internal resistance would require measurements throughout the SoC-window, and use the techniques as described in the section 2.3.3.

If the battery pack passed the visual inspection, digital inspection and power cycle, the battery test was passed and it can be used for 2nd life applications. The data would be stored, and the battery would then be grouped in battery system, where further testing of the whole BESS system over longer periods is performed. While not being part of the battery test, battery issues would sometimes be discovered in this stage, as some issues would only be visible during prolonged cycling.

4. Results and discussion

Figure 11 shows a summary of the calculated resistance for all the 12 battery modules tested. The two plots on the left show resistance obtained with ICI, while the plots on the right show resistance obtained with GITT. The plots on the top show the total resistance, while the plots on the bottom show the instantaneous resistance. Each plot shows all six battery modules for the 84% SoH battery (BAT1) and for the 96% SoH battery (BAT2). The resistances are the average resistance from all measurements done between 40% and 60% state of charge. The limits of the Y-axis are the same for all plots in this figure, showing that GITT and ICI give roughly the same results for BAT1 and BAT2, although trends between modules do not hold up between the two measurement techniques. Trends between the modules do however hold between the instantaneous and total resistance. An example to illustrate this: module 4 has the highest resistance as measured by GITT, while for ICI it is module 5 that has the highest resistance. However, the highest resistance for GITT and ICI is the same, regardless of whether one considers total resistance or instantaneous resistance. We also see that the total resistance is around twice as high as the instantaneous resistance, and that the 84% SoH battery consistently has higher resistance than the 96% SoH battery, illustrating the close link between resistance and degradation of Li-ion batteries.

Some key takeaways from these plots are: the aged battery has, as expected, higher resistance for all modules. GITT and ICI give similar results. There is a significant difference between the instant resistance and the total resistance, suggesting that processes such as diffusion are significant. We see no clear trends between the module resistances, suggesting that thermal experience of the modules has not been very different inside the same battery, although lesser variations could be hidden by the noise in the measurements. Also, for instance, the ICI measurement of BAT1 module 3 seems a bit off, but it's hard to tell whether it is statistically significant. There is no similar trend in the GITT measurements, which makes it less likely to be something with the actual module. All in all, these measurements suggest that both ICI and GITT can be useful for assessing the health of used EV batteries, and that both can easily distinguish between a used and a slightly used battery, while spotting minor differences between different modules seems challenging with the data and modelling at hand here.

Figure 11: Summary of resistances found for the different batteries and modules.

Figure 12 shows the full data set for module 2 for both BAT1 and BAT2. The first row of plots shows the characteristic pulses and relaxations for ICI and GITT. Here, it can be clearly seen that different currents were used for the 84% SoH and the 96% SoH batteries. In the second row the difference in capacity for the two battery modules can be seen, while the third and fourth rows show the calculated instant and total resistances, respectively. The data points are plotted with decreasing opacity with increasing time. The fifth row shows voltage as a function of capacity, including also the characteristic ICI and GITT voltage drops and relaxations. BAT1 (84% SoH) has slightly higher potential during both charge and discharge compared to BAT2 (96% SoH). Normally, the opposite would be expected, but this could be explained by the higher currents used for BAT2. The total polarization for both BAT1 and BAT2 are quite similar and relatively low, indicating low internal resistance. Row six and seven show the same as row 4 and 5, just plotted as a function of capacity instead of time. Also, the average resistances of all measurements performed between 40 and 60% SoC are plotted as stars. The appendix has equivalent plots for all 12 battery modules that were tested.

As for the comprehensive data in Figure 12 there is some additional insight. We see that the ICI measurements reveal greater resolution and detail for how the resistance varies with SoC. We see a large increase in resistance for low SoC for both GITT and ICI, but it is more pronounced for the ICI measurement. The ICI measurements were performed at slow C-rate, so the increased

resolution does come at the cost of roughly twice the measurement time. However, the significantly lower C-rate is beneficial as it lowers the risk of safety-related battery incidents in the lab when doing the measurement. At the same time, there is no evidence that the much longer rest time of the GITT necessarily gives any statistically significant difference in the measured total resistance.

Figure 12: Details of ICI and GITT measurements for module 2 for BAT1 (84% SoH) and BAT2 (96% SoH).

5. Summary and conclusions

This report describes the challenges encountered with different battery diagnostic methods. The most accurate characterization techniques are often time consuming and complex, while providing detailed information on a battery's state of health. On the other hand, the faster and less complex methods lose detail and accuracy, but are more easily adopted on a commercial scale. In the work reported here, we have attempted to meet somewhere in the middle by exploring methods normally used for cell-level diagnostics, on modules. The testing and diagnostic methods currently used by ECO STOR to diagnose the battery packs they receive from their EV partners are also described for comparison.

It is important for commercial stakeholders to have access to diagnostic methods which can provide as accurate information as possible in a reasonable timeframe, and without being destructive. GITT and ICI are both methods which we have shown here to provide information on remaining capacity and internal resistance. In addition, GITT also gives OCV for all relaxation points. A full GITT or ICI test can be performed in a day and give quite detailed information. In order for this type of information to be useful, it is often necessary to have similar data for a new battery system which has not been used. Otherwise, the values reported may not be of any value. In this case, we had 6 modules at 96% SoH and 6 modules at 84% SoH, thus we have good data for comparison.

From the data, it is a clear trend that the 84% SoH modules have higher internal resistance compared to the 96% SoH modules. This is true for all measurements, both instantaneous and total resistance, although with some variation. There are, however, some variations in the modules, which indicates that the degradation is not even across the battery pack. The two methods, GITT and ICI, both give quite similar values for resistance, showing that both methods would be good alternatives for diagnosing a battery with respect to resistance only. The advantage of GITT is that it also provides information on OCV. GITT has fewer relaxation points along the charge and discharge curves compared to ICI, which may cause some loss of information. It is also possible to perform GITT at more frequent intervals. However, this would significantly increase the time required to perform the tests. Thus, GITT and ICI, while also overlapping, seem to complement each other.

Although both GITT and ICI provide significant information about the battery module, which can be used to diagnose the battery and define its suitability for further use, these methods do not provide any information about the different degradation mechanisms in the battery. It is not possible to find out if the battery is degraded due to lithium plating, electrolyte degradation, transition metal dissolution, or other degradation reactions. However, if a second life stakeholder has good collaboration with the EV manufacturer, which can provide access to the BMS, these methods may be sufficient tools for determining whether or not a battery is suitable for further use.

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ANNEX 1 – GITT data for all modules

The following section shows all the data acquired for the battery modules using GITT. The legend for each figure shows which battery module the data is for. These figures show both direct measurements as well as values calculated based on these measurements.

ANNEX 2 – ICI data for all modules

The following section shows all the data acquired for the battery modules using ICI. The legend for each figure shows which battery module the data is for. These figures show both direct measurements as well as values calculated based on these measurements.

